

Detection and spectrophotometric determination of some phenols

Seema Dixit*, Ram Parkash and S. K. Mehta

Department of Chemistry and Center of Advanced Studies in Chemistry, Panjab University,
Chandigarh-160 014, India

E-mail : seemadixit@yahoo.com Fax : 91-172-2545074

Manuscript received 22 February 2005, revised 11 July 2005, accepted 14 July 2005

We report the detection and spectrophotometric determination of microgram quantities of some phenols on the basis of their reaction with 1,5-diphenylcarbazide in presence of KMnO_4 .

In view of the widespread presence¹⁻³ and toxicity⁴ of phenols and their derivatives their detection and determination⁵⁻⁸ has become a subject of great interest for analytical chemists. However, most of these methods are either time consuming or less selective than desired. In the present communication, a sensitive and selective procedure is reported for the detection and spectrophotometric determination of microgram quantities of some phenols based on their reaction with 1,5-diphenylcarbazide in presence of KMnO_4 .

Results and discussion

The fact that mono- and di-hydroxyphenols react with 1,5-diphenylcarbazide in the presence of an oxidizing agent (KMnO_4) forming a red colour serve the basis for the present work. Phenols on oxidation give phenoxy radical which is very unstable and undergoes rapid transformation thereby forming a phenoxide ion. Phenoxide ion reacts readily with 1,5-diphenylcarbazide at the carbon atom forming a negatively charged addition product. Its formation is well supported by the fact that only anion exchange resin gives red colour. Alternatively, the unstable

phenoxide ion may take up a proton from the NH group adjacent to carbon atom.

Phenol, α -naphthol, β -naphthol, thymol, orcinol and resorcinol give red colour both in solution and resin phase. No colour reaction was observed in case of trihydroxy phenols. The plot of absorbance of the red complex as a function of wave lengths shows a plateau with a maximum absorbance at 520 nm. Beer's law is obeyed for solutions containing amounts indicated in Table 1 under the optimum conditions.

The effect of diphenylcarbazide and KMnO_4 concentration and variation in time and temperature on the absorption of the red complex were examined. It was found that 0.5 ml of 0.1% diphenylcarbazide and 0.04 ml of 0.01% KMnO_4 are the most suitable. The reaction is complete in 5 min and it gives the maximum absorbance. The optimum temperature was found to be 60°C, after which there is no change in absorbance. These phenols are detected in the presence of large amounts of foreign substances; no interference was given by hydrocarbons and their derivatives, alcohols, ethers, carboxylic acids,

Table 1. Limits of identification and spectrophotometric determination of phenols

Compd.	Identification limit, (μg)		Determination limit $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$	Amount (μg)		Standard deviation	C.V.	% Error
	Solution phase	With resin bead		Taken	Found			
Phenol	3.8	1.9	0.47-3.29	0.94	0.93	± 0.61	0.021	+0.8
α -Naphthol	4.4	1.4	0.72-5.04	1.44	1.45	± 0.78	0.033	-0.9
β -Naphthol	4.4	1.4	0.72-5.04	2.16	2.14	± 0.90	0.046	-1.3
Thymol	7.5	3.0	0.75-5.25	1.50	1.51	± 0.79	0.032	+1.0
Resorcinol	6.6	2.2	0.55-3.30	1.65	1.63	± 0.81	0.049	+1.2
Orcinol	5.7	2.8	0.72-4.32	1.44	1.45	± 0.78	0.031	-0.9

carbohydrates, heterocyclic bases, aldehydes, ketones, amides, nitriles and amines. The bead test has an edge over the aqueous test as this is more sensitive. Detection limits for both tests are presented in Table 1. The resin beads thus, serve to concentrate the phenol and act as detection medium to improve the sensitivity of the test. The tolerance limits of the following compounds in the determination of 40.0 µg of phenol are given in parenthesis : *o*-nitrophenol (5.0), *p*-nitrophenol (3.0), *o*-cresol (3.0), *m*-cresol (4.0), nitrophenol (5.0), *p*-nitrophenol (3.0), *o*-cresol (3.0), *m*-cresol (4.0), phloroglucinol (3.5), pyrogallol (8.0), vanilline (2.0), aniline (1.5), creatine (1.0), thiourea (1.0), nicotine (2.0) and quinol (8.5).

Experimental

Detection in solution phase :

A drop of 1,5-diphenylcarbazine (0.1% solution in 98% methanol) and one drop of KMnO₄ (0.1% aqueous solution) were added to a drop of phenol test solution (0.1 M in 98% methanol). The contents were heated at 60 ± 2°C for 10 min. A red colour develops, if the test solution contains a mono- or di-hydroxy phenol.

Ion-exchange resin bead test :

About 4-6 ion-exchange resin Amberlite IRA 400 beads (OH⁻ form) were placed on a white spot-plate and blotted dry with filter paper. A drop of test solution, followed by a drop each of 1,5-diphenylcarbazine and aqueous KMnO₄

solution were added to it. The resin beads turn red, if the test solution contains mono- or di-hydroxyphenol.

Determination :

An aliquot of phenol containing 0.50–6.0 µg, 1,5-diphenylcarbazine (0.5 ml) and KMnO₄ solution (0.04 ml) were diluted with methanol to 10 ml and heated at 60 ± 2°C for 5 min. Absorbance of the resulting red solution was measured by a UV/VIS spectrophotometer model V-530 in a 1-cm cuvette at 520 nm against a reagent blank at room temperature (25–30°C).

References

1. S. S. Gupta, M. Stadler, C. A. Noser, A. Ghosh, B. Steinhoff, D. Lenoir, C. P. Horwitz, K-W. Schramm and T. J. Collins, *Science*, 2002, **296**, 326.
2. M. J. Spence, S. H. Bottrell, J. J. W. Higgo, I. Harrison and A. E. Fallick, *J. Contam. Hydrol.*, 2001, **53**, 305.
3. M. Kawahigashi, K. Kaiser, K. Kalbitz, A. Rodionov and G. Guggenberger, *Global Change Biology*, 2004, **10**, 1576.
4. M. W. Jung, D. W. Lee, J. S. Rhee and K. J. Paeng, *Anal. Sci.*, 1996, **12**, 981.
5. F. Feigl, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1960.
6. G. Kovacevic, M. Bodirolga and O. Jasminka, *Vojnosanit Pregl.*, 1991, **48**, 405.
7. K. Robards, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2003, **1000**, 657.
8. M. Uchida and A. Okuwaki, *J. Solution Chem.*, 2003, **32**, 19.